

Instructions:

These materials are designed for use with workshop "Click Here if You Agree (to Reclaim the EdTech Classroom through Speculative Co-design)" by Michał Wieczorek (UCD) and Eamon Costello (DCU). Artwork by Bryan Mathers (Visual Thinkery).

Example: The Ultimo Chair

BIRDS EYE VIEW

LEG X ——— X LEG
SAFE ZONE
LEG X ——— X LEG

- ★ Every child should have their place in the classroom
- ★ Available in many sizes and colours for a customizable sitting experience
- ★ Fully biodegradable

ULTIMO CHAIR

FROM **ecoSIT**

For a more comfortable personal experience

- ⚠ To maintain safety, all four legs of the EcoSit chair should touch the floor while the product is in operation.
- ⚠ The EcoSit chair comes unassembled. The manufacturer does not assume responsibility resulting from incorrect assembly.
- ⚠ All wood used to manufacture the EcoSit chair comes from sustainable Amazon rainforest logging.

Badges of Approval

Warnings of non-compliance

Badges of Approval

Warnings of non-compliance

